

A Study on the Effectiveness of Synthetic Bags

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Vasantha, M & Senthil Kumar, P. "A Study on the Effectiveness of Synthetic Bags." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 6–11.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532915>

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Introduction

The worldwide environment is varying day by day and at the moment it has become a face to living life forms that every inhabitant is trying to develop their countries lacking the environmental effectiveness of degradation. More and more factories are gradually established and harmful chemicals are used in the manufacturing process. People are using Synthetic bags, which are environmentally hazardous products, for their regular needs chiefly for shopping purposes as a result of which, the environment and agricultural lands are thereby being polluted. Therefore, it is try to reduce the environmental as well as agricultural land pollution, consumers of Synthetic bags and the business organizations together can play a major role.

Significance of the Study

Synthetic bags dumped into the earth prevent the production of nutrients in the soil. Because of this, the fertility of the soil is reduced and affects the agriculture sector. Not only human health, it dangerously special effects other animal life and alters the environment sustainability causing hazardous pollution. The study attempts to point out the effectiveness s of Synthetic bags on the environment and propose a few alternatives for Synthetic bags to make a sociable environment.

Objectives of the Study

- To appreciate the types and disposal of Synthetic in the background.
- To carry out the environmental effectiveness of Synthetic bags.
- To study the alternatives available to return the usage of Synthetic bags
- To identify the policy of Synthetic industry in India
- To understand the above concepts and present suitable suggestions for a gracious environment.

Clearance of Synthetic S

When Synthetic s are used, second-hand, or disposed of left in the surroundings as litter, they break down and release dangerous chemicals. These pollutants have heavy metals such as cadmium and lead, and chemicals such as benzene, dioxins, and other pollutants, which all release injurious toxins into our air, water, and bodies. Flaming of Synthetic in incinerators releases deadly heavy metals and chemicals. Incinerators produce a variety of deadly discharges to the air, water, and ground that are important sources of powerful pollutants, including dioxin and other chlorinated organic compounds that are well known for their venomous effects on human health and the environment. In landfills, leachate is formed when water picks up toxins as it seeps through the trash. Although landfills try to gather this venomous leach ate, it also leaks into ground and surface water, releasing pollutants into the environment and causing health risks for persons and nature.

Environmental Effectiveness of Synthetic Bags

Direct Environmental Effectiveness

This is further divided into

a) Ingestion

Animals by chance eat the Synthetic s thrown on the marine while feeding on their natural food. This leads to starvation or malnutrition and may also cause internal injuries. These Synthetic substances have chemical venomous substances which may also cause death.

b) Embarrassment

Embarrassment can lead to suffocation, starvation, drowning, increased vulnerability to predators, or other injury among animals and other living organisms.

c) Environment Variation

This is not only limited to marine animals but also plants; other immobile living organisms and sensitive ecosystem are affected due to marine debris.

Indirect Environmental Effectiveness

This is classified into

a) Ecosystem Alteration

Efforts to eliminate marine debris can harm ecosystems. Mechanical beach raking uses a tractor or other mechanical device to eliminate marine debris from beaches and marine shorelines and can adversely effectiveness shoreline habitats.

b) Invasive Species

Marine debris can contribute to the transfer and movement of invasive species. Floating marine debris can carry invasive species from one eliminate to another.

Principle of Synthetic Industry in India

The increase of Synthetic small-scale processing and reprocessing industries started in the decade of eighties with the declaration of the new industrial policy. Synthetic processing and reprocessing industries are also exempted from monitoring by Pollution Control Board.

- Prohibit the use of Synthetic materials in sachets for storing, packing or selling.
- No food stuffs will be authorized to be packet in recycled Synthetic s or compostable Synthetics,
- recycled carry bags to have precise BIS standards, colour to the prescription by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS),
- Standardized thickness shall not be less than 40 microns in carry bags etc.

Alternatives to Synthetic Bags**Paper Bags**

Paper bags have traditionally been presented as the environment friendlier option when compared to Synthetic bags. Prior to the introduction of jute bags, paper bags were the most commonly used for shopping purposes. The natural fibres of paper and the renewable resource used has a positive image, as the raise in volume of the paper bags, likely to be sent to the landfill, have now taken over a new role in the recycling options which are firmly established. It has been scientifically proven that paper bags are not harmful to the environment as Synthetic bags.

Recyclable Synthetic Bags

Recyclable Synthetic bags are being manufactured in Synthetic industries which are less injurious to the soil and surroundings. Synthetic bags manufactured which are non-recyclable or recyclable both are made of ingredients and unsafe to the environment. So, substitute recyclable bags which are not made of Synthetic s are most welcome.

Table 1.1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Variable	Class	Frequency	%
1	Age	18 – 25	190	34.4
		26 – 30	270	48.8
		31 – 50	73	13.2
		Above 50	20	3.6
Total			553	100
2	Gender	Male	360	65.1
		Female	193	34.9
Total			553	100
3	Marital Status	Single	354	64
		Married	199	36
Total			553	100
4	Education	Primary School	38	6.9
		High School	77	13.9
		UG	141	25.5
		PG	152	27.5
		Diploma	145	26.2
5	Occupation	Private	367	66.4
		Public	44	8
		Self – Employee	90	16.3
		Student	29	5.2
		Retired	10	1.8
		Homemaker	13	2.4
Total			553	100
6	Income	Searching for a Job	42	7.6
		5000 – 10000	107	19.3
		10001 – 15000	269	48.6
		15001 – 25000	135	24.4
Total			553	100

Source: Primary Data

Results in table 4.1 indicate the following outputs:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age

- The highest percentage of the age group 26 -30 is 48.8 % while the lowest is 3.6% from the age group of above 50 years of the respondents.

Gender

- The research denotes that 65.1% are Male, while 34.9% are Female.

Marital Status

- The largest respondents of 64% are married and 36% of the respondents are unmarried.

Education

- Most of the respondent’s education level is Post Graduate (27.5%). Meanwhile, only 6.9% of respondents are Primary School level.

Occupation

- Majority of 66.4 percentages of the respondents are working in private sectors. Meanwhile, only 1.8 percent of the respondents are retired.

Table 1.2
Users Level of the Synthetic Bags

S. No	Variables	Class	Frequency	%
1	Private Business	Never	354	64.0
		Rarely	142	25.7
		Often	57	10.3
		Very often	0	0.00
Total			553	100
2	Individuals	Never	353	63.8
		Rarely	200	36.2
		Often	0	0.00
		Very often	0	0
Total			553	100
3	Families & Schools	Never	0	0.00
		Rarely	94	17.0
		Often	212	38.3
		Very often	247	44.7
Total			553	100
4	Retail Stores	Never	0	0.00
		Rarely	182	32.9
		Often	206	37.3
		Very often	165	29.8
Total			553	100
5	Hotels Services	Never	0	0.00
		Rarely	112	20.3
		Often	278	50.3
		Very often	163	29.5
Total			553	100

Source: Primary Data

Users Level of the Synthetic Bags

Private Business

The largest percentages 64% of the respondents never utilized the Private Business, while 25.7% of the respondents are rarely using the Private Business and only 10.3% of the respondents are often using the Private Business.

Individuals

63.8% of the respondents are not using the Individuals while only 36.2 % of the respondents are rarely using these Individuals.

Families & Schools

This analysis shows that all the respondents are using the FAMILIES & SCHOOLS services in following levels. 44.7 % of the respondents are using the FAMILIES & SCHOOLS services very often and 38.3 % of the respondents are using these services in often level. 17.0 % of the respondents are rarely using these FAMILIES & SCHOOLS services.

Retail Stores

The above table reveals that all the respondents are using the Hotels in following levels. 37.3 % of the respondents are using the Retail Stores in often level, 32.9% of the respondents are using rarely and 29.8% of the respondents are using very often.

Hotels

The above table indicates that all the respondents are using the Hotels in following levels. 50.3 % of the respondents are using the Hotels in often level, 29.5% of the respondents are using very often and 20.3% of the respondents are rarely using the Hotel services.

Environmental Value

The environmental value is not to be confused with environmental evaluation is the process of putting monetary values on environmental good and services. Many of which have no easy observed market prices.

Economic Value

The economic value is a measure of the benefit provided by goods or services to an economic agent.

Table 1.3
Usefulness and Moral Values of the Synthetic Bags

H0: There is no relationship between the usefulness of Synthetic bags and its moral values.

S. No	Dimensions		Moral Values		Total
			Environmental Value	Economic Value	
1	Usefulness	Convenient	92	108	200
2		Not Convenient	58	142	200
Total			150	250	400

Sources: Primary Data

Table 1.4
Chi-Square Test

H0: There is no relationship between the usefulness of Synthetic bags and its moral values.

S. No.	Dimensions	Observed Frequency (F0)	Expected Frequency	(F0 - FE)	(F0 - FE) ²	(F0-FE) ² / FE
1.	AB	92	75	17	289	3.85
2.	Ab	108	125	-17	289	2.31
3.	.aB	58	75	-17	289	3.85
4.	.ab	142	125	17	289	2.31
Calculated Value						12.32

Sources: Primary Data

Result

The table value of X² for 1 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.841. The calculate value (12.32) of chi-square test is much higher than this table value and hence the result of the experiment does not support the hypothesis.

Findings

- 61.33 %, 92 respondents are use the Synthetic bags for more convenient purpose, but they are well know the environmental values.
- 43.20 %, 108 respondents are used the Synthetic bags for more convenient, but they are not care our environment value.
- 38.67%, 58 respondents are not used the Synthetic bags because they very well know the environmental values.
- 56.80%, 142 respondents are not used the Synthetic bags because they care about the economic values.

Conclusion

The modern environment including the basic needs of the soil, water and air is seriously affected by the use of Synthetic bags. Synthetic bags are manufactured with fossil fuel which leaves out venomous gas has become damaging to the various life forms in the earth. Inconsiderate disposal of Synthetic bags after use and lack of proper management in non-industrial countries are also causing difficulty to the environment. To bring public awareness, the regional and national different levels of educational curriculums must take account of the waste management systems from the grass-roots as information resources. In addition to bringing out public awareness on the importance of a healthy environment, mechanisms of controlling the generation of wastes at the basis alternative disposal ways, establishing additional drop-off areas and incineration mechanisms, Synthetic recycling facilities are also recommended. Use of Synthetic bags can be reduced through codification by imposing heavy taxes or fees on the production of them.

Web Sites

- <http://www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/ijld/article/download/4137/3583>
<https://jchps.com/specialissues/Special%20issue3/18%20jchps%20si3%20P.Pavani%2087-93.pdf>
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